

CONTROL OF MECHANICAL PROPERTIES ACCORDING TO CONTENT RATIO OF COPPER COATED CARBON NANOTUBES IN ALUMINUM COMPOSITES

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1. Introduction

Since the demonstration of Bacon about graphite whiskers in 1960 [1], carbon fibres have been extensively applied as reinforcement materials of metal matrix composites. They have been utilized in a wide variety of applications such as the field of aircraft, automotive, aerospace, ship, sporting goods, military supplies and construction before the discovery of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) by Iijima in 1991 [2]. CNTs have superior mechanical properties such as high young's modulus about 1TPa and tensile strength about 150GPa than those of steels [3-5], as well as very high thermal conductivity [6] and excellent electrical properties [7,8]. For these reasons, numerous studies have been conducted at research area of CNTs reinforced metal matrix composites by rapidly replacing those of carbon fibres in the last decade. Consequently, various synthetic methods have been proposed for the manufacture of CNTs reinforced metal matrix composites; for example, powder metallurgy [9-11], melting and solidification[12], thermal spray[13,14], electrochemical deposition[15,16], and other unique methods[17].

In recent years, many research groups have reported on eye-opening results about CNTs reinforced aluminum (Al) matrix composites using the most popular powder metallurgy (PM) technique [9-11]. In the case of CNT reinforced Al matrix composites, the PM process typically consists of four basic steps: The first step is the preparation of powders which consist of CNTs and Al matrix, the second step is powder mixing and blending, the third step is compaction, the fourth step is sintering. Regardless of respective steps, there have been still many issues to be solved in utilizing CNTs as reinforcement in Al matrix, for example, formation of agglomeration of CNTs in Al matrix, poor distribution of CNTs throughout the Al matrix, weak interfacial adhesion between CNTs and Al matrix, bad chemical and structural stability of CNTs in Al matrix. Those problems lead to deterioration of the

mechanical properties of Al-CNT composites. Therefore, homogeneous distribution of CNTs throughout the Al matrix and excellent bonding at Al/CNT interface through the suitable fabrication technologies must be certainly realized for improvement in various properties of Al-CNT composites.

Here, we systematically investigated the improved strength performances according to the content of the ball-milled Copper (Cu) coated MWCNTs (Cu/MWCNTs) composite powders in Al matrix using molecular level mixing technique, followed by the combination of spark plasma sintering (SPS) and hot extrusion process for homogeneous dispersion and good bonding at the MWCNTs and Al interface. In the case of 2 wt% Cu/MWCNTs reinforced Al composites, the tensile strength and yield strength are about 320 MPa and 187 MPa, which are about 3.2 times and about 4.4 times higher than those of pure Al, respectively. It is considered that the introduction of the appropriate Cu coated on the surface of MWCNTs plays an important role in uniform distribution of MWCNTs within Al matrix, enhancing good interfacial strength between two interfaces and efficient stress load transfer through MWCNTs in Al matrix.

2. Experimental

2.1. Synthesis and purification of MWCNTs: MWCNTs have been synthesized by thermal decomposition of C_2H_4 gas over Fe-Mo/MgO catalyst at 800°C for 1hr using catalytic chemical vapor deposition method [18]. And then, raw MWCNTs were highly purified by ultrasonication at room temperature in H_2O_2 solution [19].

2.2. Fabrication of MWCNTs reinforced Cu matrix nanocomposite powders: The reduced Cu/MWCNT composite powders were fabricated by molecular level mixing technique [17]. 920 mg of $Cu(CO_2CH_3)_2 \cdot H_2O$ and 200 mg of MWCNTs were homogeneously mixed by sonication process in 100

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ml of ethanol solution. And then, diethylene glycol of 100 ml was added to above suspension. The solution was vaporized with magnetic stirring at 140°C, and was subsequently gone through drying, calcination and reduction process. Finally, Cu/MWCNTs composite powders were collected.

2.3. Fabrication of Cu/MWCNTs reinforced Al matrix nanocomposite powders: We used conventional ball mill process with weight ratio (1:15) of two mixed powders and alumina balls for 5 hr, resulting in obtaining highly dispersed Al-0.5~2 wt% Cu/MWCNTs powders. [10].

2.4. Manufacture of Al-Cu/MWCNTs nanocomposites through compaction, sintering and hot extrusion process: Above ball-milled Al-Cu/MWCNTs powders were sealed and pre-compacted by canning and degassing process in heating reactor with aluminum die (50 mm x 60 mm) at 350°C for 1hr. And then, spark plasma sintering (SPS, ELTEK Co., Korea) process was carried out for 10min at 550°C in a graphite mold under a pressure of 10^{-2} torr to synthesize Al-Cu/MWCNTs nanocomposites. The pre-compacted powders were highly densified and consolidated. Finally, for manufacturing fixed diameter extrudates, hot extrusion of the compact was conducted at 500 °C using an extrusion ratio of 15:1 [11].

2.5. Characterization of the Cu/MWCNTs powders and Al-Cu/MWCNTs composites: The morphology and component of powders and fracture surfaces of extrudates were characterized by using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (JEOL, JSM-6701F) and Energy dispersion spectroscopy (EDS) which was performed in the EDAX-equipped SEM. The microscopic structure is also examined by high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) (JEOL, JEM-2100F, 200 kV). For TEM evaluation, the specimens was prepared by triple beam Focused Ion Beam (FIB) (Japan SII, SMI 3050TB). The tensile strength was measured by a universal testing machine (Japan, AG-I 50 kN).

3. Results and discussion

As shown in Fig.1, surface and component analyses on Cu/MWCNTs nanocomposite powders were examined by SEM and EDS, respectively. Fig.1(a) shows SEM image of Cu/MWCNTs nanocomposite powders. MWCNTs were coated with Cu in order to conduce homogeneous distribution in Al matrix and better bonding of adjacent interface between MWCNTs and Al matrix using molecular level

mixing technique [17]. Cha *et al.* reported that CNTs were more implanted and located within composite powders rather than on the surface of those. However, unlike the their research results, we obtained the better results about fairly uniform Cu coatings on the surface of MWCNTs as well as pretty much protruded Cu-coated MWCNTs on the surface of the Cu/MWCNTs nanocomposite powders, as shown in inset of Fig.1(a). This result is very effective to good dispersion, homogeneous distribution and strong interfacial bonding with Cu coated MWCNTs in Al matrix. This can lead to strengthening on overall mechanical properties. Fig.1(b) is EDS spectrum obtained from the same area of SEM image of Cu/MWCNTs nanocomposite powders. A large peak of Cu is obviously observed in the EDS spectrum. It clearly indicates that Cu is extensively well coated on the overall surface of MWCNTs.

Fig.1. (a) SEM image of Cu/MWCNTs nanocomposite powders, inset is high magnified SEM image of Cu coated MWCNTs, (b) EDS data of Cu/MWCNTs nanocomposite powders at the same area.

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Fig.2 is high resolution SEM image showing the morphology of well dispersed and embedded 2 wt% Cu/MWCNTs powders in Al matrix using ball mill process for 5 h. Previously, many researchers have reported improvement in mechanical properties by the addition of appropriate CNTs content in Al matrix [9-11]. For the first time, Kuzumaki *et al.* described the enhanced mechanical properties of 5 or 10 vol % CNT reinforced Al composites, accompanied by no formation of carbide at the interfaces in the Al-CNT composites [9]. A. Esawi *et al.* have utilized planetary ball milling to disperse 2 wt% MWCNT in Al matrix, but resulted in considerable strain hardening of Al matrix and formation of large spheres [10]. But, in our case, ball milling for up to 5hr lead to good dispersion of 2 wt% Cu/MWCNTs powders in Al matrix without the damage of CNTs and the formation of large spheres, as shown in Fig.2. Also, we could not observe pores and structural defect sites between Cu/MWCNTs and Al matrix in Al-Cu/MWCNTs powders. Kwon *et al.* reported that the slight addition of 5 vol% CNTs could remarkably increase the mechanical properties [11]. When CNTs content is exceeded within a restricted volume fractions of Al-CNTs composites, it is more likely to develop the agglomeration of CNTs which results in deterioration in the mechanical properties. Moreover, those research groups insisted that homogeneous dispersion, good alignment and strong interfacial bonding were absolutely necessary to produce an advanced Al-CNTs composites. In addition to the concentration control of Cu/MWCNTs in Al matrix, it is necessary to optimize ball milling conditions such as mill time, component ratio, intensity,

Fig.2. SEM image of Al-2 wt% Cu/MWCNTs nanocomposites fabricated by ball milling for 5h

ambient atmosphere and grinding media for achieving homogeneous distribution and good reinforcement of Cu/MWCNTs in Al matrix.

With ball-milled Al-Cu/MWCNTs powders, the highly densified and consolidated Al-Cu/MWCNTs nanocomposites were fabricated by using SPS, followed by hot extrusion techniques [11]. The oxide-destroying effect of the SPS process and better

Fig.3. (a) Optical image (×50), (b) low magnified TEM image, and (c) high magnified TEM image of longitudinal cross sections of the extrudate prepared by SPS and hot extrusion process

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densification of hot extrusion route lead to further improvement in density and mechanical strength of Al-Cu/MWCNTs nanocomposites. Fig.3(a) is optical image ($\times 50$) of the longitudinal cross section of the extrudate for Al-Cu/MWCNTs nanocomposites fabricated by SPS and hot extrusion process. The direction of Cu/MWCNTs was horizontally aligned to the extrusion direction in Al matrix. The relative density of above 98% was obtained from 2 wt% Cu/MWCNT content. Kuzumaki *et al.* already showed that the CNTs aligned along the extrusion direction had good mechanical properties withstanding the load of the extrusion direction [9]. However, they did not mention the results about homogeneous distribution of CNTs in Al matrix. Fig.3(b) shows TEM image of the longitudinal cross section corresponding to Fig.3(a). The arrow is pointing the Cu/MWCNTs infiltrated in Al matrix. In our experimental, Cu/MWCNTs in Al matrix are well dispersed and also located parallel to the extrusion direction.

Kwon *et al.* confirmed that good dispersion and regular orientation of CNTs in Al matrix as well as formation of aluminum carbide (Al_4C_3) affected strong bonding at the interface between the CNTs and the Al matrix had a beneficial influence on enhancement in mechanical strength [11]. Generally, it is well known that Al_4C_3 is easily formed when CNTs are annealed at high temperature above Al melting point [20]. Also, defect sites of CNTs, amorphous carbon and carbonaceous particles cause chemical reactions of CNTs with Al matrix, resulting in Al_4C_3 formation. But, we have observed no formation of Al_4C_3 between two phases in Al-Cu/MWCNTs nanocomposites made by using SPS and hot extrusion process, as shown in Fig.3(c).

Fig.4. SEM image of fractured surface of Al-Cu/MWCNT nanocomposites (Inset image is the specimen used for the tensile test)

It is assumed that the uniform coating of Cu in Cu/MWCNTs powders restrains formation of Al_4C_3 , as well as strengthens interfacial bonding between MWCNTs and Al matrix.

Fig.4 is SEM micrograph showing the fractured surface of the specimen of Al-Cu/MWCNT nanocomposites after the tensile test (See inset image of Fig.4). There exists to be a lot of dimple and microvoid patterns which is a small hollow with the size of around $1\mu m$ on the fracture surface of Cu/MWCNT nanocomposites, related with moderately ductile fracture after some necking. The fracture surface has a very irregular and rough appearance. Cu/MWCNTs are homogeneously observed in the Al matrix. This indicates that Cu/MWCNTs are uniformly dispersed in Al matrix. Occasionally, strong interfacial interaction between cracks and Cu/MWCNTs is shown in Fig.4. Some Cu/MWCNTs are mutually connected perpendicular to the crack direction and bridged between the cracks of each other. This crack-bridging effect can make possible to improve the fracture toughness of Al-Cu/MWCNTs nanocomposites.

The mechanical properties of the Al-Cu/MWCNT nanocomposites were characterized as a function of Cu/MWCNTs content, as shown in Fig.5. From the strain versus stress graph, content ratio of Cu/MWCNTs composites in Al matrix have remarkably influence on mechanical properties such as tensile strength, yield strength and elongation. Deng *et al.* have reported that Al-1 wt% CNTs composites exhibited the mechanical characteristics were higher than those of Al-2wt% CNTs composites fabricated by cold isostatic pressing followed hot extrusion techniques [21]. While Al-2wt% CNTs composites showed the decrease of the relative density and interface debonding, Al-1wt%

Fig.5. Mechanical properties of Cu/MWCNTs content

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CNTs composites exhibited the highest mechanical properties compared with those of pure 2024 Al. Also, they noted that the elongation of below Al-1wt% CNTs composites kept almost invariable, owing to highly flexible elastic behavior of the added CNTs. However, in our results, tensile strength and yield strength was increasingly improved according to the increase of additive contents of Cu/MWCNT powders in Al matrix. When 1 wt% Cu/MWCNTs are reinforced in Al matrix, tensile strength and yield strength were about 270 MPa and 141 MPa, which are more than about 2.7 times and 3.2 times higher than those of pure Al, respectively. But, the elongation of Al-1 wt% Cu/MWCNTs is about 23%, which is about 0.4 times a little lower than that of pure Al. On the other hand, when 2wt% Cu/MWCNTs were applied to Al matrix, the mechanical strengths were much higher than that of Al-1wt% Cu/MWCNTs nanocomposites. However, the elongation of 2wt% Cu/MWCNT reinforced Al composites is about 13 %, which is about 0.4 times a little lower than that of Al-1wt% Cu/MWCNTs. Although the high tensile and yield strength are obtained in Al-2wt% Cu/MWCNTs nanocomposites, the elongation is in inverse proportion to the Cu/MWCNTs content. When 0.5~1wt% Cu/MWCNTs are appropriately introduced in Al matrix, the similar value of elongation is obtained. This values are slightly higher than that of Deng et al. This indicates that the proper Cu/MWCNTs content is an important another factor affecting the mechanical properties Al-Cu/MWCNTs nanocomposites.

4. Conclusions

The improved mechanical properties were obtained from the introduction of homogeneously dispersed and good bonded Cu coated MWCNTs in Al matrix. Also, we controlled the change of mechanical properties according to the content ratio of Cu/MWCNT composite powders in Al matrix. Addition of the proper Cu/MWCNTs powders which are well distributed in Al matrix leads to high mechanical stiffness. It is considered that the introduction of the appropriate Cu coated on the surface of MWCNTs plays an important role in uniform distribution of MWCNTs within Al matrix, enhancing good interfacial strength between two interfaces and efficient stress load transfer through MWCNTs in Al matrix.

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